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Olive grove microbiome

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Deliverable 4.1 Olive grove microbiome

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Executive Summary

This deliverable from the SOIL O-LIVE project describes the core and accessory microbiomes of olive tree roots across the Mediterranean Basin under different agricultural practices (organic, traditional, and superintensive or hedgerow). Analysis of 472 rhizospheric soil samples from Portugal, Spain, Morocco, Italy and Greece revealed that the country of origin primarily drives the overall microbial community (bacteria and fungi) structure (beta-diversity). In the second position the sampling site has an effect rather than the management type. In other words, the type of agricultural management of the olive grove has a marginal influence on the structure and composition of the microbial communities. A more detailed and in-depth analysis is necessary to determine if these differences are due to geography, climate (more or less humidity, as a starting hypothesis) or the cultural/agronomic tradition of each site.

The study identified the most abundant bacterial phyla (Proteobacteria and Actinobacteria) and fungal phyla (Ascomycota) in each country, highlighting country-specific dominant genera. Further analysis identified core bacterial (25 genera, dominated by Actinobacteria) and fungal (3 genera: *Fusarium*, *Cladosporium*, and *Mortierella*) microbiomes common across the Mediterranean basin. Interestingly, the specific genera associated with each type of olive grove management varied significantly between countries, suggesting that "traditional," "organic," and "superintensive" practices are implemented differently across the region, potentially due to local traditions and agricultural methods. This country-specific response to management practices warrants caution when attempting to establish a universal rule for how land management modifies olive rhizosphere microbial communities. However, the identified common core microbiome offers promising avenues for future biotechnological applications in olive cultivation.

1. Introduction

The results of Task 4.1 (*Analysis of the microbial communities of the olive rhizosphere*) allowed us to know the core and accessory microbiomes of olive trees grown under different agronomical practices. The overall objective of Work Package 4 “*Microbiome of olive groves*” of the SOIL O-LIVE project is to analyse the microbial communities of the olive rhizosphere in three types of olive groves management across the Mediterranean Basin.

The present deliverable constitutes the first outcome of Work Package 4 with the “*Description of the core and accessory microbiomes of roots from olive trees grown under different agronomical practices*”. This enables the intercomparison among the different microbial communities of the olive rhizosphere of the SOIL O-LIVE sites distributed across the Mediterranean region under different pedoclimatic and management conditions.

2. Materials and Methods

Rhizospheric soils samples were obtained from 12 olive trees per orchard at full bloom during May 2023 in Portugal, Spain, Morocco and Greece; unfortunately, in Italy some groves were sampled at September 2023 which caused a delay. The sampling was done in 20 organic, 21 traditional and 11 superintensive (hedgerow) orchards which generated 472 rhizospheric soil samples across the Mediterranean basin. Environmental DNA was obtained from all samples with DNeasy PowerSoil Pro Kit (Qiagen; Hilden, Germany), and sequenced at Instituto de Parasitología and Biomedicina López Neyra (CSIC, Granada) by Illumina technology with a MiSeq equipment and a PE300 strategy according to Cardoni et al. (2023). The prokaryotic communities (Bacteria and Archaea) were analyzed with amplicons of the 16S rRNA gene (hypervariable regions V3 and V4) while the fungal communities were analyzed with amplicons of the ITS2 region (Wentzien et al 2024). In this way, we obtained near 40 and 47 Millions raw reads of bacterial and fungal sequences, respectively. This amount of reads was enough to assess the microbial diversity according to the rarefaction curves.

Figure 1. Bacterial (left) and fungal (right) rarefaction curves

After the trimming process these amounts were 22 and 30 Millions of sequences which yield 10,611 and 5,411 ASVs (Amplicon Sequence Variants, equivalents to species) for bacteria and fungi, respectively. The analyses for ASVs obtaining, alpha and beta diversity indices, taxonomical assignment, etc. were done with our own Micro4all workflow (Wentzien et al. 2023) which is free available at GitHub in https://nuriamw.github.io/micro4all/tutorial/package_workflow.html.

3. Results

According to the results obtained in Task 4.1, where the microbial community of each olive tree was analysed separately without pooling by treatment neither by plot, the beta-diversity analyses showed that the rhizosphere microbial communities were separated by the country of origin and not by the kind of land management. Thus, further studies of the different agronomical practices cannot be done all together (i.e. pooled). In contrast, they must be done for each country in order to identify common tendencies between geographical regions and olive groves management. The first step was to identify the most abundant bacterial and fungal phyla and genera in each country. The taxonomic profiles showed that the phylum Proteobacteria was the most abundant, between 50% and 60%, in samples from Portugal, Italy and Greece while in samples from Spain and Morocco the phylum Actinobacteria was predominant with a relative abundance *circa* 40%. At genus level *Pseudomonas* was highly abundant in samples from Portugal, Greece, Morocco and Italy while in the Spanish samples it was nearly absent. At the same time, as a mode of country fingerprint, some specific genera were very abundant in each country like *Neobacillus* in Portugal, *Citrobacter* in Italy, *Pseudarthrobacter* in Morocco or *Rubrobacter* in Spain. Interestingly, most of the genera (near 70%) in Spain were unclassified or with an average relative abundance below 1%, which implies a high diversity and evenness.

Figure 2. Bacterial composition at phylum level

Figure 3. Bacterial composition at genera level

The fungal phyla showed a similar trend to that of the bacterial phyla, with Ascomycota as predominant in all cases, although in Portugal, Italy and Greece its relative abundance was around 80% while in Spain and Morocco reached about 50%. In this last country a high abundance of phylum Mortierellomycota (> 30%) was also observed while in the other countries only reached 5%. Moreover, rhizosphere samples from Spain showed about 30% of phylum Basidiomycota and near 10% of Glomeromycota that was almost absent in soils from the other 4 countries.

Figure 4. Fungal composition at phylum level

Figure 5. Fungal composition at genera level

At genus level the situation was very similar to that observed with the bacterial genera. While *Fusarium* was highly abundant in samples from Portugal, Italy and Greece (above 30% in all cases), in samples from Morocco and Spain the relative abundance of this genus was always below 10%. It must be point out that the genus *Fusarium* contains pathogenic but also beneficial species interacting with plants. The most abundant fungal genus in samples from Spain was *Solicoccozyma* while in Morocco *Mortierella* highlighted as the most prevalent.

In order to identify the core and accessory microbiomes in relation to olive groves management, data of each country were compared internally after a global analysis to obtain a common table of ASVs across the olive orchards of the Mediterranean Basin. In this way, we obtained 11,460 common bacterial ASVs which belong to 615 genera. After filtering to those genera with relative abundances higher than 0.1%, nearly 100 bacterial genera present in the 5 countries and the 3 types of groves management were identified. Regarding the fungal communities, and implementing the same criterion, 5,411 ASVs belonging to 740 genera were identified with approximately 100 genera displaying relative abundances higher than 0.1%. After implementing this approach, and once the corresponding tables of genera were obtained, the first step was to identify the core microbiome for each treatment and country. According to the current literature the criterion to be considered as part of the core microbiome was that a genus must be present in at least 85% of the samples of each country and type of agronomic management.

With these criteria, we made the comparison in each country among the 3 core microbiomes of each treatment. The results for Spain showed that only one bacterial genus was specific for the traditional management while in Morocco and Greece 3 genera were identified and 10 for Portugal. *Nitrosospira* was present in traditional samples from Spain and Portugal, but it was not

specific for this management in the other countries. Moreover, we could not detect any other bacterial genus present at the same time in the traditional samples of the other countries. The analyses of Italian samples are inconclusive since there was no sampling of any high-density/superintensive orchard.

In samples from Greece no core genus specific for the organic olive orchard treatment was identified, and only one in the case of Portugal (genus *Curtobacterium*). Samples from organic management groves from Spain and Morocco showed 8 and 6 specific genera, respectively, although no genus was shared between these two countries. In soils from the superintensive hedge-row olive orchards management system no specific genus was found in Spain and Portugal, while 3 genera were identified in Morocco orchards and 28 in samples from Greece. The genera *Priestia*, *Cytobacillus* and *Modestobacter* were shared between both pools of samples.

Figure 6. Bacterial core and accessory microbiomes by countries and olive groves management. In all plots green circle means organic, yellow circle traditional and red circle high-density or superintensive olive management. The number inside each circle means the number of core genera specific of that treatment or the common core genera to all interactions among treatments.

The bacterial genera that constitute the core microbiome of the olive rhizosphere across the Mediterranean Basin were *Streptomyces*, *Sphingomonas*, *Gp16*, *Solirubrobacter*, *Gaiella*, *Nocardioides*, *Mycobacterium*, *Tepidisphaera*, *Gp6*, *Pseudarthrobacter*, *Neobacillus*, *Kribbella*, *Microvirga*, *Niallia*, *Pseudonocardia*, *Gp3*, *Subdivision3_gis*, *Spartobacteria_gis*, *Reyrabella*, *Bradyrhizobium*, *Blastococcus*, *Gp4*, *Rhabdothermincola*, *Geodermatophilus* and *Nitrospira*. That is to say, there is a major representation of phylum Actinobacteria, which may reflect the climatic conditions of the Mediterranean Basin (drought and high temperature), followed by genera of the Proteobacteria phylum.

The fungal communities of the olive groves across the Mediterranean Basin showed a situation similar to that of the bacterial ones. In the high-density, hedge-row system no specific genus was identified for samples originating from Spain, while 2 genera were found for Morocco, 3 for Portugal, and 18 for samples of Greece orchards. No information could be obtained for Italy since this cropping system was not implemented in orchards selected for this country.

Figure 7. Fungal core and accessory microbiomes by countries and olive groves management. In all plots green circle means organic, yellow circle traditional and red circle hedge-row or superintensive olive management systems. The number inside each circle means the number of core genera specific of that treatment or the common core genera to all interactions between treatments.

It should be pointed out that none of 23 fungal genera, specific for the high-density cultivation system were shared among countries; that is to say, the samples of each country have their own specific fungal genera for this kind of agronomic management.

The traditional treatments showed no specific genera for samples from Spain and Italy, 1 and 2 genera in samples from Morocco and Greece, respectively, and 12 fungal genera in the rhizosphere soil samples from Portugal. Among these 14 fungal genera, *Lophiotrema* was the only one shared between Morocco and Portugal, while 2 genera were specific from Greece and 11 from Portugal.

Samples from groves subjected to organic management in Greece have no specific genera. Results from Italy were not conclusive since no high-density/superintensive management was available under this cultivation regime. Finally, 3 (Portugal) 6 (Morocco) and 19 (Spain) specific genera were identified in samples originating from this cropping system. This kind of land management did not share fungal genera between samples of Portugal and Morocco. The comparison with the Spanish samples showed that genera *Theλονectria*, *Penicillium* and *Tetracladium* were present also in rhizosphere soil samples from Morocco. The remaining genera were specific of each country. The common fungal core genera for all treatments and countries was constituted by *Fusarium*, *Cladosporium* and *Mortierella*.

4. Conclusions

These results indicate that the number of genera present in the core microbiome of the olive rhizosphere is very low across the Mediterranean Basin. This fact could be interesting in order to provide future biotechnological solutions based on the use of microorganisms since potential candidates are present within this small pool of genera. Another question is the selection of specific genera for each kind of olive orchard management since they are specific for each country. This suggests that the “traditional”, “organic” and “high-density/superintensive” managements, and without excluding other factors, are somehow different in each country, what could be a consequence of their own idiosyncratic traditions and agricultural practices. In some countries the “traditional management” could be more “industrial” and similar to a low intensive management system than that implemented in other countries, which otherwise may depend on the advent of more modern (mechanical, chemical, ...) means of management. Thus, a general rule for the modification of the microbial communities due to the type of land management in olive orchards should be taken with caution while a common rhizosphere core microbiome could be well defined and established.

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